

1 **Catabolism of Acetosyringone and Co-metabolic Transformation**
2 **of 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol by a Novel FAD-dependent**
3 **Monoxygenase**

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14 **Supplementary information**

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16 **Methods**

17 *Mineral medium solution*

18 The mineral medium (MM) was composed of solution A (109.55 g $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 27 g
19 KH_2PO_4 , 10 g $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ in 1000 ml distilled water, pH 7–7.5, autoclave-sterilized), solution
20 B (0.3 g $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ dissolved in 50 ml distilled water, filter-sterilized), solution C (2 g MgSO_4
21 dissolved in 50 ml distilled water, filter-sterilized), and solution D (0.1 g FeSO_4 dissolved in 50
22 ml distilled water, filter-sterilized) where 900 ml of sterile distilled water was initially mixed
23 with 100 ml of solution A and then 5 ml of solutions B, C and D was added. Minimal medium
24 (MM) was stored at 4 °C for short-term use; otherwise, it was freshly prepared prior to each
25 experiment.

26 *Stock solutions*

27 Acetosyringone (AS) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany), as were the other
28 substrates and pollutants unless stated otherwise. The AS stock solution for cultivation was
29 prepared at a concentration of 0.1 M in ethanol for UV spectroscopy (Lach-Ner, Czech
30 Republic) and filter-sterilised.

31 To reduce the number of samples required during the initial screening of the transformation
32 potential of the bacterial consortium ASC12 toward selected aromatic pollutants (APs) and
33 chlorophenols (CPs), mixtures of pollutants were prepared. All pooled pollutant solutions were
34 prepared by mixing stock solutions of individual pollutants, each at a concentration of 2 mM in
35 DMSO (Lach-Ner, Czech Republic), in order to minimise potential synergistic toxicity effects.
36 The pollutants (all Sigma-Aldrich, Germany unless stated otherwise) were grouped as follows:
37 i) phenol (Lach-Ner, Czech Republic), 2-chlorophenol (2-CP), 2,6-dichlorophenol (2,6-DCP),
38 2,4,6-trichlorophenol (2,4,6-TCP), ii) 3-chlorophenol (3-CP), 3,5-dichlorophenol (3,5-DCP),
39 2,3,4,5-tetrachlorophenol (2,3,4,5-TeCP), iii) 4-chlorophenol (4-CP), 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-
40 DCP), 2,4,5-trichlorophenol (2,4,5-TCP), pentachlorophenol (PCP), iv) bisphenol A, diethyl
41 ether, and v) dibutyl phthalate, diphenyl phthalate. Remaining pollutants, namely naphthalene,
42 biphenyl, phenanthrene, and dibenzofuran, were analysed individually.

43 For the individual-compound setup, stock solutions of the tested pollutants, namely phenol, 2-
44 CP, 3-CP, 4-CP, 2,6-DCP, 3,5-DCP, 2,4-DCP, 2,4,6-TCP, 2,4,5-TCP, 2,3,4,5-TeCP, and
45 pentaCP, were individually prepared by dissolving each compound in DMSO to a final
46 concentration of 10 mM.

47 Stock solutions of selected lignin building-blocks, namely AS, caffeic acid, coumaric acid,
48 eugenol, ferulic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, Japan), guaiacol, orcinol, protocatechuate,
49 dihydroxyphenylacetate, 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, sinapic acid, vanillic acid, vanillin and
50 veratric acid (MCE, USA) were individually prepared by dissolving each compound in DMSO
51 to obtain final concentrations of 10 μ M; 0,1 mM; 1 mM; 2 mM and 3 mM and 10 mM.

52 ***HPLC-PDA analysis***

53 Briefly, the samples were analysed by reverse-phase HPLC (Shimadzu Nexera XR equipped
54 with SPD-M20A DAD) using an Arion 5 μ m C18 Plus 100x4.6 column with a flow rate of 0,8
55 ml/min at 40 °C. Mobile phase A consisted of deionised water, and phase B was HPLC-grade
56 methanol, both containing 0.02% (v/v) trifluoroacetic acid (Supelco, Germany). The retention
57 times and working concentration range (0–500 μ M) of all tested compounds were determined
58 by analysing standards of corresponding pollutants. All the analyses were performed by the
59 following method: 0–2 min: 8–25 % B; 2–6 min: 25–90 % B; 6–9 min: 90 % B; 9–10.5 min:
60 90–25 % B; 10.5–14 min: 25–8 % B. Integration of peaks and post-run analysis was conducted
61 in Shimadzu's LabSolution software.

62 ***Quality control and assembly of the sequencing data***

63 Quality control of Illumina short reads was performed using bbdduk.sh v39.06 (parameters:
64 ktrim=r k=23 mink=11 hdist=1 tpe tbo qtrim=r trimq=10 ftm=5;
65 <https://sourceforge.net/projects/bbmap/>) with the BBMap-supplied adapters.fa file. For
66 Nanopore long reads, adapter trimming and quality filtering were conducted using Porechop
67 v0.2.4 (default settings; (1)) and Filtrlong v0.2.1 (--min_length 1000 --keep_percent 90;
68 <https://github.com/rrwick/Filtrlong>).

69 Assembly of the sequencing data was carried out using two strategies: Flye v2.9.4 (2) for long-
70 read-only assembly, and hybridSPAdes (3) v4.0.0 for hybrid assembly of both short and long
71 reads. Contigs from individual assemblies were binned into metagenome-assembled genomes
72 (MAGs) using SemiBin2 v2.1.0 (multi_easy_bin mode) (4). MAG quality was assessed using
73 CheckM2 v1.0.2 (5), and dereplication was performed with CoverM v0.7.0 (cluster --ani 99 --
74 quality-formula Parks2020_reduced) (6). MAGs were functionally annotated using the NCBI
75 Prokaryotic Genome Annotation Pipeline (2024-07-18.build7555) (7) and taxonomically
76 classified with GTDB-Tk v2.4.0 (8).

77 ***The expression of candidate genes***

78 Cells from 50 ml of the O/N culture induced with 0.3mM IPTG were harvested by
79 centrifugation, washed twice with MMS, and resuspended in 5ml 50 mM NaH₂PO₄, 300 mM
80 NaCl, pH = 8, and immediately used for enzyme activity assay. Enzyme active assays were
81 conducted similarly to RCAs described above, with some modifications. Briefly, suspensions
82 of induced cells were washed and adjusted to OD₆₀₀ = 10 in MM, as a biotic control, *E. coli*
83 BL21(DE3) cells bearing an empty pET19b plasmid were used. For the enzyme activity assays,
84 250 µl of the cell suspension (OD₆₀₀ = 10) was incubated with 2.5 µl of 10 mM control
85 substrate: vanillin, ferulic acid, vanillic acid, protocatechuate, dihydroxyphenylacetate, and AS
86 chosen based on the annotated function of the candidate genes, at 12 °C for 48 hours with
87 shaking. Similarly, all candidate genes were also tested for their ability to deplete 2,6-DCP and
88 2,4,6-TCP. The reactions were stopped with methanol, processed by vortexing, sonication, and
89 centrifugation. The resulting supernatants were transferred to HPLC vials for subsequent
90 HPLC-PDA analysis. All samples were prepared in triplicate.

91 ***The preparation of the AS1-derived biosensor strain and the induction assay***

92 The pTr-egfp backbone and IR DNA sequence were PCR-amplified and fused employing the
93 NEBuilder HiFi DNA Assembly Master Mix (New England Biolabs, USA), following the
94 manufacturer's protocol. *E. coli* DH5α transformants were selected on solid LB plates amended
95 with 2 µg/ml of tetracycline. The sequence of the resultant plasmid pTr-IR-egfp was verified
96 by Sanger sequencing, and it was inserted into AS1 cells by electroporation (Choi et al., 2006)
97 (9). Transformants were selected on LB medium with tetracycline (2 µg/ml). Transformants
98 were transferred to fresh LB plates with tetracycline, and the presence of the plasmid pTr-IR-
99 egfp in transformed cells was verified by PCR using isolated plasmid DNA (QIAprep Spin
100 Miniprep Kit, Qiagen). For the induction assay, the AS1 cells bearing pTr-IR-egfp (hereinafter
101 referred to as AS1/egfp) were cultivated O/N in liquid LB medium with 2 µg/mL tetracycline.
102 Cells were washed twice (10 minutes/5000 × rcf/18°C) and resuspended in MM 1× to reach a
103 final OD₆₀₀ of 0.1. The cell suspension was supplemented with 2 µg/mL tetracycline and
104 distributed in 200 µL aliquots into a pure Grade S flat- and clear-bottom black microtiter plate.
105 Wells were then supplemented with 2 µL of either a substrate stock solution diluted in DMSO
106 or pure DMSO (control wells). The substrates tested were 3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid,
107 acetosyringone, caffeic acid, eugenol, ferulic acid, guaiacol, *p*-coumaric acid, orcinol, sinapic
108 acid, vanillic acid, vanillin, and veratric acid in stock concentrations of 10 µM; 0,1 mM; 1 mM;
109 2 mM, and 3 mM. The microtiter plates were incubated in a Synergy H1 Plate Reader (BioTek)
110 at 28°C with continuous agitation for 96 hours. OD₆₀₀ and eGFP fluorescence at 476 nm

111 (excitation)/520 nm (emission) were measured at 1-hour intervals. To quantify the induction
112 capacity of each substrate, R ratios were obtained by normalizing the eGFP fluorescence values
113 by OD₆₀₀ readings for each well and time point, and the induction rate expressed as the fold-
114 induction relative to control wells (i.e., only DMSO added) was calculated. To rule out potential
115 interference from the substrates or their transformation products, AS1/wild-type cells cultivated
116 in plain LB medium were treated analogously alongside AS1/egfp. The induction rates of
117 AS1/egfp were then compared to the corresponding values obtained from the AS1/wild-type
118 cells to yield the relative induction rate (RI).

119 ***Identification of the initiator of AS transformation within the asdBCAD gene*** 120 ***cluster***

121 To test the transformation of AS by induced recombinant *E. coli* BL21(DE3) strains expressing
122 individual *asd* genes, a procedure similar to the RCA assay described in the main text was
123 employed. Briefly, 250 μ l of cell suspension (OD₆₀₀ = 10) was added to 4 ml glass vials,
124 followed by the addition of 2.5 μ l of a 10 mM AS stock solution. As a control, *E. coli*
125 BL21(DE3) harbouring an empty expression vector was used. All reactions were prepared in
126 triplicate. Incubations were carried out at 28 °C and 150 rpm for 24 hours. To terminate the
127 reactions, 250 μ l of HPLC-grade methanol was added to each vial. Before HPLC-PDA analysis,
128 cells were removed by centrifugation at maximum speed for 3 minutes, and the supernatants
129 were transferred to fresh glass vials.

130 ***The LC-MS analysis specifications***

131 The cell suspensions were acidified by the addition of 20 μ L of 1 M HCl and extracted with an
132 aliquot of ethyl acetate (EtOAc, 2 mL; 5 times). The extracts were then dried with sodium
133 sulphate and concentrated to dryness using a nitrogen stream. Samples were diluted in 1 mL of
134 methanol and analysed with LC-MS. The separation of analyses was performed in a Kinetex
135 Polar-C18 2.6 μ m 100 Å chromatographic column (100 x 2.1 mm, Phenomenex, CA, USA).
136 The mobile phase was composed of 0.1% formic acid in water and 0.1% formic acid in
137 methanol. The flow rate was 0.4 ml/min, the column temperature was maintained at 40°C, and
138 the mobile phase gradient elution started with 5% methanol for 3.0 min and increased up 100%
139 in 15 min. After 5 min at 100% methanol, the starting conditions were established, and the
140 column was equilibrated for 5 min prior to injection of the next sample. 10 μ l of sample extract
141 was injected. For the non-target analysis, both positive and negative modes were used. QTOF
142 MS was tuned using Swarm Autotune for the mass range m/z 50–1600. For the positive mode,
143 reference m/z = 121.050873 and 922.009798 were used during the analysis to achieve the best

144 mass accuracy. Subsequently, for negative mode, reference $m/z = 112.985587$ and $m/z=$
145 980.016375 were used. A single MS mode (ESI, both polarities, 5 spectra/s) in the range 50–
146 1600 m/z was chosen to perform metabolite profiling on the cell extracts. For MS/MS analysis,
147 an autoMS/MS mode was used. Spectra were acquired using two different collision energies
148 (CE = 20 and 40 eV) and a fragmentor voltage of 110 V. The mass range was 50–1000 m/z ,
149 and the MS/MS acquisition rate was 5 spectra/s. To confirm the data, a targeted MS/MS method
150 was used. For AS in positive mode, for 2,4,6-TC/ in negative mode; set up with collision
151 energies (CE = 10, 30, and 40 eV) and fragmentor voltage 110 V in both polarities. The resulting
152 fragmentation spectra and isotopic pattern were compared with the Metlin spectra library
153 (https://metlin.scripps.edu/landing_page.php?pgcontent=mainPage).

154 The proportional transformation product amounts were calculated based on peak area as the
155 relative concentration of AS or 2,4,6-TCP equivalent in the extracts.

156

157 **Supplementary Figures**

158 i)

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160 ii)

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162 iii)

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164 **Figure 1:** Graphical representation of the metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) obtained after
 165 sequencing the ASC12 consortium, including common genomic parameters: i) MAG of *Pseudomonas*
 166 *rhizophila* AS1, ii) plasmid MAG of *Pseudomonas rhizophila* AS1 (pAS1), and iii) MAG of
 167 *Methylothera versatilis* MT1.

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172 **Figure 2:** Exemplary results showing the induction of the intergenic region (P_{IR}) in AS1 by
173 acetosyringone and orcinol. R represents the ratio of relative fluorescence units to optical density at 600
174 nm ($R = \text{RFU}/\text{OD}_{600}$). R values are plotted with standard deviation as error bars (two replicates).

175

176 **Figure 3:** Acetosyringone (AS) transformation by induced recombinant *E. coli* BL21(DE3) strains
177 expressing individual *asd* genes. The graph shows the depletion of AS by *E. coli* BL21(DE3) cells
178 carrying plasmids with *asdA*, *asdB*, *asdC*, or *asdD*. A strain harbouring an empty vector was used as a
179 control. The Y-axis represents the peak area, corresponding to the residual amount of acetosyringone in
180 the sample. Error bars represent the standard deviation from biological replicates.

182

183 **Figure 4:** Chromatogram showing the transformation of AS (missing peak of AS in black and red
184 spectra) and the detection of its transformation product (AS-OH) by *E. coli* cells expressing only the
185 gene *asdA* (in black), which is missing in the cells expressing the whole *asdBCAD* gene cluster (red).

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188 **Figure 5:** Chromatogram showing the transformation of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol (2,4,6-TCP) and the
 189 detection of its transformation products, namely, 2,6-dichlorohydroquinone (DCHQ) and 2,6-dichloro-
 190 4-methoxyphenol (DCMP) by *E. coli* cells expressing either only the gene *asdA* (in red) or the *asdBCAD*
 191 gene cluster (black), which are missing in the cells with the empty vector (biotic control) and abiotic
 192 controls (green and blue, respectively).

193 Supplementary Table

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Supplementary Table 1: Primers used in this study			
Product	Designation	5'-3' sequence *	Amplicon length [bp]
<i>16S rRNA</i> gene	8F	AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG	1501
	1509R	GYTACCTTGTTACGACTT	
	515F	GTGYCAGCMGCNCGG	411
	926R	CCGYCAATTYMTTTRAGTTT	
pET-19b backbone	pET_F	ctagcataacccttgggcctc	5576
	pET_R	ggtatatctccttctaaagttaaac	
pTr backbone	pUCP_F	atggtgagcaagggcgagg	6926
	pUCP_R	acgcctcctcacgataataag	
<i>asdABCD</i> cluster	asdA_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgaacactcatgctgatg	4722
	asd_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcagaatgggaaggagaattg	
<i>asdA</i> coding sequence	asdA_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgaacactcatgctgatg	1284
	asdA_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcagaggaactgagagcgtc	
	vdh_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgctggacgtgccctgttg	1479

<i>vdh</i> coding sequence (vanillin dehydrogenase)	vdh_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcagatcgggtaatgccgg	
<i>fcs</i> coding sequence (feruoyl CoA-synthetase)	fcs_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgagtgttgagttcagatc	1899
	fcs_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGctagtcgccccgaggatcg	
<i>ech</i> coding sequence (hydroxycinnamoyl-CoA hydratase/lyase)	ech_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgagcaattacgaaggtcgc	861
	ech_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcagcgcctgttaggtctgc	
<i>vanAB</i> cluster (vanillate <i>O</i> -demethylase)	van_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgtatccaagaacacctg	2054
	van_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAgatatccaacacaaaagtg	
<i>pcaHG</i> cluster (protocatechuate 3,4-dioxygenase)	pca_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatgactgacaagcctggttatc	1303
	pca_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcagtagtcgaagaacaccg	
<i>hpaD</i> coding sequence (3,4-hydroxyphenyl acetate 2,3-dioxygenase)	hpa_F	AGAAGGAGATATACCatggcgcaagtcgctctggc	888
	hpa_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcaaaactggaaaaatggcggtg	
	hpa_R	AAGGGGTTATGCTAGtcaaaactggaaaaatggcggtg	
intergenic region upstream <i>asdC</i>	IR_F	ATCGTGAGGATGCGTactgaacgtgacgctatcag	1300
	IR_R	GCCCTTGCTCACCATttttgactctttattattagtagg	

* 15bp 5'-overhangs enabling fusion with a plasmid backbone are capitalised.

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Supplementary Table 2: Compost soil characteristics	
Classification	Sandy loam with smooth texture
Dry matter content	83.8%
Organic matter content	23,6%
pH	8
2-4 mm particles	1,4%
Larger than 4 mm particles	1,6%

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